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URL-Based Topic Classification

UBTC

Data Management Plan (DMP)

Lead partner:	Thomas Kirz
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Deliverable abstract

This deliverable is the initial Data Management Plan (DMP) for the URL-Based Topic Classification project. It will be kept updated as a living document. The DMP addresses the relevant aspects of the management of data and other outputs produced by the project according to the principles outlined in the FAIR Data section.

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TERMINOLOGY

<https://eosc-portal.eu/glossary>

Acronym	Definition
DMP	Data Management Plan
CSV	Comma Separated Values
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	FAIR-Principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
MB	Megabyte
PDF	Portable Document Format
WP	Work Package

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. Introduction

A data management plan (DMP) is a structured document that keeps record of what research data is created or reused and what happens to that data during and after a project. It helps with planning the research process and defining responsibilities in a research project involving several researchers or institutions. For writing this DMP, we followed the [Horizon Europe DMP template](#).

Thomas James Kirz will act as the data manager who will be in charge of the actions described by this DMP.

1.2. Data Summary

- Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.
- What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?
- What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?
- What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?
- What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?
- To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

We use two datasets containing labelled URLs for training and evaluating our models. In R2, each URL is labelled with one of 15 categories (e.g. Sports, News, Gaming etc.) and in R1 each URL is either labelled with 'phishing' or 'benign' and it is used for a binary classification setup.

Pre-labelled data is crucial for the types of experiments conducted in this project, where we want to find out how well machine learning algorithms can predict a website's category by its URL.

Produced datasets:

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P1	Prediction results for DMOZ dataset	Structured text	CSV	100 MB	no

dataset ID	title	type	format	estimated volume	contains sensitive data
P2	Charts	Images	PNG	100 MB	no
P3	Prediction results for the Phishing Detection dataset	Structured text	CSV	100 MB	no
P4	Experiment Python code	Source code	Jupyter Notebooks	100 MB	no

P1 and P3 will describe which predictions were made for the URLs by the best classifier found. P2 will include charts showing which hyperparameters lead to the best classification accuracy and a confusion matrix for the classification of P1. P4 includes all code needed to run and verify the experiments, as described in a README file.

Reused datasets:

dataset ID	title	PID (e.g. DOI) or source	rights (e.g. license)	contains sensitive data
R1	Phishing Detection Dataset	10.17632/6tm2d6sz7p.1	CC BY 4.0	no
R2	DMOZ	https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/shawon10/url-classification-dataset-dmoz?select=URL+Classification.csv	CC0/CC BY 3.0 (see section 6.2)	no

1.3. Methods and software used for data generation and reuse

For each of the datasets used, combinations of classification algorithms and hyperparameters is run on the URL/category pairs of the datasets, using cross validation. Evaluation metrics are calculated and stored for each combination, and they are used to generate the charts/reports. Again using cross-validation, the respective best-performing classifiers are trained. The predictions made then make up the prediction result datasets P1 and P3.

1.4. Foreseeable research uses and /or users

The charts and reports can be helpful for researchers developing related projects and new approaches for URL classification. The prediction results will be mainly interesting to those who want to analyse and verify the findings and reproduce the experiments.

2. FAIR data

2.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

We will make our data findable, by uploading it to Zenodo, which provides a persistent identifier and adding relevant metadata. The repository will provide means for harvesting the metadata, including its machine-actionable representation.

The file names and repository structure are clearly defined in the projects README.md file. Version control is automated using Git and the GitHub – Zenodo integration.

The metadata provided includes related works referenced and datasets used, licensing information, DOI and programming languages used.

Additionally, we will provide common metadata such as title, description, or keywords when publishing data. In this case, we will follow the default template provided by the repository.

No controlled vocabularies are relevant for this experiment's data.

2.2. Making data accessible

We will make our data accessible by providing open access to data by publishing it to Zenodo, with a retention period of at least 20 years.

dataset ID	access conditions	restrictions / embargo reasons	estimated publication date	location for publication (repository)	PID	license
P1	Open	None	2024-04-30	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.11093040	CC-BY-4.0
P2	Open	None	2024-04-30	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.11093040	CC-BY-4.0
P3	Open	None	2024-04-30	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.11093040	CC-BY-4.0
P4	Open	None	2024-04-30	Zenodo	10.5281/zenodo.11093040	GPL-3.0-or-later

Repository description:

ZENODO builds and operates a simple and innovative service that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to share and showcase multidisciplinary research results (data and publications) that are not part of the existing institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities. ZENODO enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to: easily share the long tail of small research results in a wide variety of formats including text, spreadsheets, audio, video, and

images across all fields of science. display their research results and get credited by making the research results citable and integrate them into existing reporting lines to funding agencies like the European Commission. easily access and reuse shared research results. <https://zenodo.org/>

Methods or software needed to access and use data: No special software is needed for accessing the data, as it will be either image-based or CSV files.

2.3. Making data interoperable

We will make our data interoperable by providing and describing data in a way that is common within our domain. As far as possible, we will use controlled vocabularies for our data to allow inter-disciplinary interoperability and machine-actionability. We will provide good documentation for all our datasets.

2.4. Increase data re-use

We will make our data reusable by adding metadata and comprehensive Readme files to all published datasets. The descriptions will include details on the methodology used, analytical, and procedural information. Licenses for code and data will always be assigned and clearly marked. The digital research data obtained will be published Open Access under a Creative Commons CC BY license.

A script will be provided that runs the experiments, reproducing the data generation for verification. The prerequisites of Python and Python packages will be clearly documented.

The following data quality checks will be done: repeated samples or measurements (cross-validation).

3. Other research outputs

All research output will be published in line with Section 2.

4. Allocation of resources

There are no costs dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR, all services used being available for free

5. Data security

5.1. Storage and backup facilities

For the duration of the project, storage and backup of data will be ensured by the project manager.

P4 (Experiment Python code), P1 (Prediction results for DMOZ dataset), P2 (Charts), R1 (ISCX-URL2016), R2 (DMOZ), P3 (Prediction results for the ICSX-URL2016 dataset) will be stored on Institution GitLab (Uni Passau). Hourly backups are made (on premises). Hourly backups are stored for seven days, after which only one backup per day will be retained.

Additionally, P1 (Prediction results for DMOZ dataset), R1 (ISCX-URL2016), R2 (DMOZ), P2 (Charts), P3 (Prediction results for the ICSX-URL2016 dataset), P4 (Experiment Python code) will be stored on GitHub.

5.2. Data security and protection of sensitive data

We pay strict attention to compliance with the relevant institutional and national data protection policies.

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any sensitive data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

Access to data during research:

dataset ID	selected project members	all other project members	the public
P1	writing	writing	no access
P2	writing	writing	no access
P3	writing	writing	no access
P4	writing	writing	no access
R1	writing	writing	no access
R2	writing	writing	no access

During the research phase, all data will be accessible to project members. At the time of publication, it will be opened to the general public.

5.3. Long-term preservation and deletion of data

dataset ID	location for long-term storage	minimum retention period (≥ 10 years)
P1	GitHub/Zenodo	10 years
P2	GitHub/Zenodo	10 years
P3	GitHub/Zenodo	10 years
P4	GitHub/Zenodo	10 years

6. Ethical and legal issues

6.1. Personal data

At this stage, it is not foreseen to process any personal data in the project. If this changes, advice will be sought from the data protection specialist at TU Wien, and the DMP will be updated.

6.2. Intellectual property rights and ownership

The reused datasets have the following license requirements.

R1

The dataset is published under the CC BY 4.0 license, allowing reuse under attribution.

R2

The dataset's direct source (<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/shawon10/url-classification-dataset-dmoz>) indicates a dedication to the public domain under the terms of the Creative Commons CC0 1.0 code. However, the trustworthiness of this license information might be limited, as there is barely any further information about the source of the data, except that it is taken from *DMOZ*, a now defunct open WWW directory. It was closed in 2017 and succeeded by *curlie.org*.

Because *DMOZ* published their data using the CC-BY 3.0 Unported license (source: <https://web.archive.org/web/20160123180859/http://www.dmoz.org/docs/en/license.html>), *Curlie* has a license allowing reuse, and the Kaggle source apparently published their data to the public domain, we confidently assume that we can reuse this dataset. We will publish our data based on the dataset using a CC-BY 4.0 license, which is compatible with the aforementioned licenses.

6.3. Ethical issues

No particular ethical issue is foreseen with the data to be used or produced by the project. This section will be updated if issues arise.

7. Other issues

No funder or departmental procedures are applicable to the data management.